

Carbon Trading: Is the concept very volatile?

Abhijit Mitra^{1,*}, Sana Ahmed^{2,#}, Ricardo Gobato^{3,§}, Shampa Mitra^{2,◊}, and Sufia Zaman^{2,¤}

¹Department of Marine Science, University of Calcutta, 35 B.C. Road, Kolkata 700019, India.

²Department of Oceanography, Techno India University, West Bengal, EM 4 Salt Lake, Sector V, Kolkata 700091, India.

³Green Land Landscaping and Gardening, Seedling Growth Laboratory, 86130-000, Parana, Brazil.

To cite this article:

Abhijit Mitra, Sana Ahmed, Ricardo Gobato, Shampa Mitra, and Sufia Zaman. “Carbon Trading: Is the concept very volatile?”, *Parana Journal of Science and Education*. Vol. 9, No. 6, **2023**, pp. 1-13.

Received: September 9, 2023; **Accepted:** September 15, 2023; **Published:** October 1, 2023.

Abstract

Carbon dioxide is one of the major GHGs and a driver in the domain of climate change. In the drive to mitigate and adapt with the issue of climate change, carbon trading has become a vital policy instrument in majority of the countries in the World. It is also a pivotal element of the UNFCCC's (United Nation of Parties of Copenhagen Climate Change Conference) approach to tackle climate change. National or regional carbon trading schemes are now operational in many counties through a well-defined structural policy, specific for the country. Yet the trading is still in a volatile stage. Many schools think that this concept is not very realistic to combat climate change, while others consider this a strict regulation to put cap/limit on the emitters. Unfortunately, the subject is characterized by jargon, abstract concepts, mathematical formulae, and technical detail, making it hard for most people to understand its implications and evaluate its merits and demerits. This paper is a first order analysis to unravel some of this complexity by imparting thrust on three basic components – cap and trade, carbon offsets and carbon trading – which underpin the trade in carbon quotas. The case study of the highly urbanized city of Kolkata and Indian Sundarban mangrove ecosystem has been discussed in details with CO₂ – e of dominant trees to analyze the probable credit that can be received from the producer communities of these two sites that are significantly different in terms of anthropogenic footprints and ecological features.

Keywords: Carbon dioxide, CO₂, Climate change, Cap and trade, Carbon offset, Carbon trading, UNFCCC's.

*Email: abhijit_mitra@gmail.com (Corresponding Author)

#Email: sanahmed85@gmail.com

§Email: ricardogobato@hotmail.com

◊Email: mitrashampa6819@gmail.com

¤Email: zamansufia123@gmail.com

1. Introduction

The objective of the UNFCCC²³ (confirmed at the UN climate conference in Copenhagen in December 2009) is to get rid of the adverse impacts of climate change. While there is, still some debate about what the maximum temperature rise can be if this objective is to be achieved, the UN climate conferences have agreed to limit the average global rise to a maximum of 2°C. The agreement also recognized the necessity to consider strengthening the long-term global goal on the basis of the best available scientific knowledge to a global average temperature rise of 1.5°C above the pre-industrial levels although there is a great doubt in the figure of the upper limit of the temperature [1].

In the post second World War phase, there were rapid industrial, urban, and agricultural developments [2, 3, 4] and because of such developmental activities, the climate of the planet Earth exhibited substantial change in terms of atmospheric temperature, rainfall, sea level, environmental quality, biodiversity, and human health.

We have used Artificial Intelligence based Neural Artificial Auto-regressive (NAR) model to forecast the level of near surface atmospheric carbon dioxide in two different environmental set ups, namely the highly urbanized city of Kolkata (22° 34' 21.36" N, 88° 21' 50.04" E) and Sundarban mangrove ecosystem (21° 56' 58.92" N, 89° 10' 59.88" E) in the Indian sub-continent. The main concept behind this site selection is to evaluate the role of urban trees and mangroves in scrubbing the atmospheric carbon dioxide, which many power sectors and other industries can adopt as a part of their CSR or carbon offset policy.

Many low-lying island states and countries most vulnerable to climate change are considering with high priority to return as quickly as possible from the current 380 ppm CO₂ to a maximum concentration of 350 ppm CO₂, to limit average temperature rises to 1-1.5°C. Beyond these levels, climate change may pose a threat to their

existence. The caps pledged as of January 2010 by industrialized countries in the post-2012 UN climate treaty negotiations are insufficient to bring down the CO₂ concentrations below 350 ppm.

Setting a global carbon cap with uniformity is a complex task. It involves governments assessing the costs and risks of not reducing emissions, and weighing these against the costs and risks of implementing the cap, in both the short- and long-term scales.

The primary aim to setting the cap is two-fold:

- I. Decision on the policy objective, *e.g.*, keeping global warming below 2°C (and capping greenhouse gas concentrations at a maximum of 350 parts per million CO₂ or keeping global warming below 1.5°C (capping them at a much lower level);
- II. Determination on how much gas can still be emitted before concentrations pass that policy objective.

In the context of the Kyoto Protocol, the cap was set by industrialized countries collectively allocating themselves permits for 95 per cent of the emissions they had been releasing before any limits were in place. However, the concept was not full proof.

In cap-and-trade schemes, two main questions arise:

Whom the cap and how to decide on the number of permits will cover?

Two further issues are whether to provide all permits up front or in instalments, and at what price to issue them. The decision of who will be covered has far-reaching implications, which are not always immediately obvious. Should the scheme cover economic units or should participants be chosen based on their geographical location?

Under the Kyoto Protocol, geographical location was chosen as the decision-making factor: but now China and other exporting countries in the global South are arguing that a large proportion of their emissions comes from the manufacture of products that are mostly consumed in other countries covered by the Kyoto Protocol cap, and that emissions ought to be accounted for by the consumer rather than the producer. Basically it is

²Copenhagen Climate Change Conference – Dec, 2009
<https://unfccc.int/conference/copenhagen-climate-change-conference-december-2009>

³The 15th session of the Conference of the Parties to the UNFCCC and the 5th session of the Conference of the Parties serving as the Meeting of the Parties to the Kyoto Protocol took place in Copenhagen and was hosted by the Government of Denmark.

an arrow towards the developed nations of the world and their luxurious life styles and high degree of consuming manufactured products due to which the emission level exhibits an increasing trend.

In the present paper, we have selected the geographical location as the primary factor to understand the variation of carbon credits in two different environmental set-ups with significant variations in terms of emission of GHGs preferably carbon dioxide. We also attempted to relate the policies and their gaps with the CO₂ – e levels of the study area.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Study area

The city of Kolkata is noted for its high population density, cultural legacy, and the mighty River Ganges flows along the city. The population of the city is increasing at a rapid pace. In 2021, the population of the megacity of Kolkata was some 14.9 million (1.49 crore) with a population density of 22,000 persons per square km [5]. Due to availability of all types of resources like cheap cost of living and smooth transportation system, people from different parts of the Indian sub-continent have made their destinations towards this lucrative city. This has resulted in an increasing trend of population since 1950 (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Increase of population in the city of Kolkata during 1950 to 2020.

Source: [6].

A common consensus among climatologists and environmentalists is that increasing greenhouse gas emissions (GHGs) in the environment is because of humans and their uncaring lifestyle, besides deforestation and burning of fossil fuels, world over thereby altering the climate of the planet Earth. CO₂ is a major contributor to the total greenhouse effect [7]. In addition to this, the megacity of Kolkata is also exposed to industrial emissions released from several factories and industrial units [6] scattered in and around the city (Table 1).

The second site is the famous mangrove habitat of the tropics, the Indian Sundarbans, supporting 4.5 million populations. Hooghly and Matla are the two major estuaries located in the western and

central sectors respectively in the present study area. Compared to the city of Kolkata, the anthropogenic threats are relatively less in the region due to absence of industries and factories. However, emission occurs in this region from brick kilns, fish landing stations, shrimp farms (excavated at the cost of mangroves), tourism units etc. Several studies are available on the salinity profile, surface water temperature, and pH level of these estuaries [8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19]. However, very few studies have addressed the long-term variation of near surface atmospheric carbon dioxide and carbon trading of the blue carbon, which this article will attempt to bring at the surface.

Table 1: Industrial units in and around the city of Kolkata

	Name of the unit		Name of the unit
1	M/s. Garden Reach Ship Builders, Garden Reach, Kolkata.	17	M/s. Usha Fan Industry Ltd., Bansroni, Kolkata.
2	M/s. India Tobacco Co. Ltd., Garden Reach, Kolkata.	18	M/s. Bharat Brake & Valves, S.M. Avenue, Kolkata.
3	M/s. Paharpur Cooling Tower Ltd., Garden Reach, Kolkata.	19	M/s. Rescon India (P) Ltd., Behala, Kolkata.
4	M/s. General Electricals Co. Ltd., Paharpur, Kolkata.	20	M/s. Hindusthan Levers Ltd., Garden Reach, Kolkata.
5	M/s. India Foils Ltd., Taratala, Kolkata.	21	M/s. Polar Fan Industry Ltd., Behala, Kolkata.
6	M/s. Hindustan Development Corpn. Ltd., Tiljala, Kolkata.	22	M/s. Central Inland Water Transport Corp., Dock Yard Road, Kolkata.
7	M/s. Kilburn Eng. Co. Ltd., Majherhat, Kolkata.	23	M/s. British Engg. Pumps Ltd., Taratala, Kolkata.
8	M/s. Siel Hardmetal Ltd., Behala, Kolkata.	24	M/s. Bharat Process & Mechanical Engg., Ultadanga, Kolkata.
9	M/s. Indian Oxygen Ltd., Taratala, Kolkata.	25	M/s. Greaves Foseco Ltd., Taratala, Kolkata.
10	M/s. Williamson Magor Ltd., Majherhat, Kolkata.	26	Downstream units of HPL (10 Units).
11	M/s. Modern Bread Industry Ltd., Taratala, Kolkata.	27	Easy Fit Jewellery Pvt. Ltd.
12	M/s. Eveready Battery, Taratala, Kolkata.	28	Jute Mills (2 Units).
13	M/s. Britannia Biscuit Co. Ltd., Hide Road, Kolkata.	29	Mizan & Co.
14	M/s. Balmer Lawrie & Co Ltd., Hide Road, Kolkata.	30	Sree Ganesh Jewellery House Ltd.
15	M/s. Calcutta Chemical Co. Ltd., Bandel Road, Kolkata.	31	HM Biscuits Industries.
16	M/s. Boroline Industries, Chiriamore, Kolkata.	32	Gitanjali Germs Ltd.

Source: [6]

2.2 Analysis of near-surface atmospheric CO₂

A portable CO₂ analyser (Lutron CO₂ meter, GCH-2018) was used to measure the near-surface atmospheric carbon dioxide concentrations in and around the selected stations during the study period (April, 1984 to April, 2022). As a part of quality assurance, 65 readings were taken during the afternoon hours at each site at 5 m apart and finally the average value was considered for further statistical analysis. This exercise was performed during the month of April for the entire study span of more than three decades.

2.3 Stem biomass estimation

The non-destructive method was used to determine the stem biomass for each tree species in which the measurement of Diameter at the Breast Height (DBH) was done after evaluating the circumference with a measuring tape and height using a laser beam (BOSCH DLE 70 Professional model). Spiegel Relaskop⁴ was used to determine the Form Factor according to the standard method outlined by the researchers [20]. The stem volume (V) was determined as per the expression

⁴W. Bitterlich, The Spiegel Relaskop (2023)
<https://www.silvanus.at/relaskop-en>

$$V = F \cdot H \cdot \pi \cdot r^2,$$

where, H is the height of the target tree, F is the form factor and r is the radius of the tree derived from its DBH.

The stem core of each species was used to estimate the species-wise specific gravity (G) and using the expression

$$AGSB = GV,$$

the above ground stem biomass (AGSB) was calculated. The exercise was carried out during April 2022 at both the selected sites.

2.4 Stem Carbon estimation

Direct estimation of percent carbon was done by CHN analyzer (Vario MACRO Elementar). The analysis was carried out with a portion of fresh stem sample of target trees of each species (collected from the same coordinate in both the sites) after oven drying at 70°C, mixed randomly and grounded to pass through a mesh size of 0.5 mm. The value obtained was converted to stored carbon per species (in tons) considering the AGBS (above ground stem biomass) for each species and their respective number (in the 10m × 10m quadrat).

2.5 Policy analysis

The research on carbon-trading schemes can be divided into three broad phases (Figure 2). The first phase is on the schemes themselves (with the primary objective to lower the carbon dioxide/emission level using green technology), such as studies conducted by several researchers [21, 22]. The most important uncertain variable in a carbon-trading scheme is the carbon price, although the research on carbon price is relatively large [23, 24]. The second category is the trading phase, i.e., what causes the fluctuation in carbon price; for example, research by Alberola et al. (2008) [25]. The third category is the research on the consequence variables of the schemes and carbon price, which implies, what social and economic impacts are brought about by a carbon-trading schemes, such as research by Li and Lu

(2015) [26]. This can be referred to as the outcome phase.

Figure 2: Phases in carbon trading scheme.

Source: Authors.

Because of the complexity of literature on carbon trading, many scholars have already reviewed this field. Hepburn (2007) [27] reviewed the carbon-emissions trading system arrangements in the Kyoto mechanism; Duan et al. (2014) [28] reviewed China’s carbon emissions trading pilot; Yu and Xu (2017) [29] used Cite Space to conduct a co-citation visual analysis of a carbon-trading scheme; Narassimhan et al. (2018) [30] comprehensively reviewed the implementation of carbon-trading schemes in eight regions. These literature reviews summarize the relevant research on carbon trading schemes locally and statically, but lack a comprehensive understanding of the dynamic process of the development and evolution of carbon-trading schemes. This paper focuses on few policies with their merits and demerits.

3. Results

We monitored the CO₂ level at two sites for more than three decades (1984 – 2022) and observed relatively high level in the city of Kolkata, India (412.85 ± 17.60) compared to Sundarbans (Indian Part) (350.44 ± 29.24) as shown in Figures (3) and (4). The predictions till 2050 also exhibit an increasing trend touching a value of 568 ppm at Kolkata (a value of concern) and 473 ppm at Indian Sundarbans mangrove ecosystem.

Figure 3: Predicted near surface atmospheric CO₂ values for the city of Kolkata during April using Nonlinear Autoregressive Neural Network Model; real time data from 1984 -2022 has been used to train the model.

Source: Authors.

Figure 4: Predicted near surface atmospheric CO₂ values for the Mangrove ecosystem of Indian Sundarbans during April using Nonlinear Autoregressive Neural Network Model; real time data from 1984 -2022 has been used to train the model

Source: Authors.

The stored carbons in the dominant trees of the two sites were monitored to assess the CO₂ – e level of each species (Figures 5 – 8).

Figure 5: Stored carbon in the Above Ground Stem Biomass in the dominant trees in the city of Kolkata, India.

Source: Authors.

Figure 6: Stored carbon in the Above Ground Biomass in the dominant trees in the mangrove ecosystem of Indian Sundarbans

Source: Authors.

Figure 7: Carbon dioxide - equivalent in the dominant trees in the city of Kolkata, India.

Source: Authors.

Figure 8: Carbon dioxide -equivalent in the dominant trees in the mangrove ecosystem of Indian Sundarbans.

Source: Authors.

This step of estimation of species-wise CO₂-e (on which the valuation depends) is done by a third party. An independent third-party auditor, known as the validation/verification body (VVB), assesses the project's emissions reduction claims by comparing project emissions to the baseline emissions. This step involves validating the project's baseline scenarios, monitoring processes, and methodologies for calculating emissions reductions. It consists of a desk review and field visit to confirm that the project meets the requirements of the carbon certification programme, like Verra's VCS. The carbon certification standard must accept the VVB to process the project registration.

4. Discussion

The concept of carbon trading is still in an embryo stage as there are many gaps in the system structure. The entire carbon credit process can be sub-divided into five major phases in the credit cycle as stated here:

- ❖ Phase 1: Project development;
- ❖ Phase 2: Project validation/verification;
- ❖ Phase 3: Project registration and carbon credit issuance;
- ❖ Phase 4: Sale/purchase of carbon credits;
- ❖ Phase 5: Retirement of carbon credits.

Phase 1: Project development

The developers design and implement projects with the primary aim to reduce the greenhouse gas emissions. This may encompass steps like reforestation, renewable energy installations, methane capture, waste management, sustainable agricultural practices, emission neutral livelihoods etc. Each project must adhere to specific methodologies or protocols specific to a certain kind of carbon project that quantify the emissions reduction potential. Project developers then outline the project activities using a specific methodology in the Project Design Document (PDD). Internationally recognized or accepted methodologies/carbon certification standards include the Verified Carbon Standard (VCS), the Gold Standard, the American Carbon Registry (ACR), and the Climate Action Reserve (CAR). DGB Group's reforestation and afforestation projects are all verified using leading standards,

such as the VCS and the Gold Standard, to ensure they deliver top-tier carbon credits and sustainable, positive results. After the project design, the PDD is approved by the certifier, and the project developer can start to develop the project in accordance with the PDD. During this phase, the project developer monitors the project's progress and execution. For reforestation projects, for instance, it entails planting thousands to millions of trees and ensuring they are retained and healthy in order to capture the project's target emissions. Several proxies like survival rate, plant biomass, chlorophyll content of the leaf and stem, growth rate etc., can be used to assure the result of plantation.

Phase 2: Project validation/verification

The validation/verification body (VVB), which is an independent third-party auditor assesses the project's emissions reduction claims by comparing the project emissions to the baseline emissions. This step involves validating the respective project's baseline scenarios, monitoring processes, and methodologies for calculating emissions reductions. It consists of a desk review and field visit to confirm that the project meets the requirements of the carbon certification programme, like Verra's VCS. The carbon certification standard must accept the VVB to process the project registration.

Phase 3: Project registration and carbon credit issuance

Once the project has successfully passed the validation and verification process, it is registered with an approved registry, such as Verra. Carbon credits issued can have various names, depending on where they are registered. Verified carbon credits under Verra's VCS are called Verified Carbon Units (VCU); under the Gold Standard, they are called Verified Emission Reduction (VER). Each VCU/VER represents 1 ton of carbon CO₂-e emissions and is assigned with a unique serial/identification number so that it can be tracked across its life cycle in the project database in context to carbon trading.

Phase 4: Sale/purchase of carbon credits

Carbon credits act as proxy currency in the carbon trading system. Once issued, they embark on a

journey through the carbon market, finding their way to individuals, investors, businesses, and even governments looking to offset their emissions. The pricing of carbon credits varies based on factors such as the project's type, location, co-benefits, and the overall supply and demand in the market. In the compliance market, carbon pricing instruments such as carbon taxes and Emissions Trading Systems (ETS) are the main drivers of carbon pricing. Understanding these pricing mechanisms helps buyers make informed decisions about their investments.

Phase 5: Retirement of carbon credits

The carbon credits can be purchased and sold like any other commodity, and their ultimate purpose is to offset emissions. After a company decides to use a carbon credit to offset/reduce its carbon emissions, the credit gets retired. This means the

registry cancels the carbon credit, and it is permanently taken out of circulation and cannot be traded or used for offsetting purposes anymore.

Retirement ensures that the emissions reduction represented by the credit is not claimed by multiple parties, preventing double counting, and maintaining the integrity of the carbon market.

India's country-level social cost of carbon emission was estimated to be the highest at \$86 per ton of CO₂-e. It means the Indian economy will lose \$86 by emitting each additional ton of CO₂. India is followed by the US, where the economic damages would be \$48 per ton of CO₂ emission. Saudi Arabia is close behind at \$47 per ton of CO₂ emission. In the present study, the species – wise CO₂-e prices for both the sites (considering the present valuation of \$ 51/ton of CO₂-e [31] are highlighted in Figure (9) and (10).

Figure 9: Cost of Carbon dioxide equivalent in the dominant trees in the city of Kolkata, India.

Source: Authors.

Figure 10: Cost of Carbon dioxide equivalent in the dominant trees in the mangrove ecosystem of Indian Sundarbans.

Source: Authors.

The cost, however, varies from country to country as a function of several taxes and permit of emission. Carbon pricing puts an explicit price on GHG emissions expressed as a monetary unit per ton of carbon dioxide equivalent (CO₂-e). The effective carbon rate is the sum of market-based instruments (specific energy taxes, carbon taxes and carbon emission permit prices) applied to carbon emissions. Explicit carbon pricing meanwhile puts a price directly on greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Two instruments that fall into this category are the carbon tax, which is a price-based instrument and the emissions trading system, which is a quantity-based instrument. Implicit carbon pricing is used in a variety of ways and refers to policies that impose compliance costs (*i.e.*, an implicit price) on activities that emit GHGs. Internal carbon pricing is when organizations assign a monetary value to GHG emissions in their policy analysis and decision making.

There are several demerits of Carbon trading through trees, which are listed here:

- I. May not reduce emission at a very high scale, as trees take time to grow and during decomposition, they may act as a source rather than sink.
- II. Extreme levels of red tape for project developers, which means only large projects have the probability to cover up the development cost.
- III. May not be cost effective, which may limit their use to only large companies and governments who can afford them.
- IV. Non-uniformity in the socio-economic structure of the nations due to which the price may fluctuate.
- V. Diseases, survival rate, biomass of the trees may be severely affected by environmental parameters and difficult to control.

5. Summary

Trees play a significant role to minimize carbon dioxide levels in the atmosphere. The estimates given in this paper are based on limited field data and may become more uncertain as they refine from national to regional and state estimates. More field measurements are needed both in the city of Kolkata and Sundarban mangrove ecosystem in the Indian sub-continent to help improve carbon accounting and other functions of the producer communities. More field data are needed to assess regional variation in forest structure; long-term permanent plot data are needed to assess tree growth, biomass, regeneration, and mortality; and improved satellite monitoring of tree cover types is needed to assess changes more accurately in urban forest cover. In addition, research needs to develop better urban tree biomass equations, improve estimates of tree decomposition and maintenance emissions, and investigate the effect of soil/environmental parameters on carbon storage and flux in any ecosystems. A better understanding and accounting of ecosystems can be used to develop management plans and national policies that can significantly ensure environmental, food and human health security.

Acknowledgement

The authors acknowledge the support of the team members from Future Corners Contracting Est., Saudi Arabia. The mangrove nursery raised at Mastorah, Saudi Arabia sparked the interest of Indian researchers of Techno India University, West Bengal to understand the scopes and challenges of evaluating mangrove carbon credit.

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